

Modular synthesis of (borylmethyl)silanes through C1 difunctionalization

Rajdip Chowdhury, Gábor Zoltán Elek and Abraham Mendoza*

Dept. of Organic Chemistry, Arrhenius laboratory, Stockholm University, 106 91 Stockholm
(Sweden)

Corresponding author email: abraham.mendoza@su.se

Table of Contents

1. General Information.....	1
2. Preparation of Starting Materials	2
2.1 General procedure A: Preparation of Grignard-reagents	2
2.2 General procedure B: Reaction of freshly prepared Grignard-reagents (using general procedure A) with diisopropylchlorosilane	3
General procedure C: Synthesis of alkoxysilanes using DMAP and triethylamine	3
General procedure D: Synthesis of alkoxysilanes using imidazole	3
Synthesis of diisopropyl(pent-4-en-1-yl)silane (2d).....	4
Synthesis of (4-chlorobutyl)diisopropylsilane (2e)	4
Synthesis of (3-(benzyloxy)propyl)diisopropylsilane (2f).....	5
Synthesis of (4-fluorophenyl)diisopropylsilane (2i)	5
Synthesis of ((4-(diisopropylsilyl)phenyl)ethynyl)trimethylsilane (2l)	6
Synthesis of diisopropyl(thiophen-2-yl)silane (2m)	6
Synthesis of (cyclohex-2-en-1-yloxy)diisopropylsilane (2r)	7
Synthesis of diisopropyl((4-methylpentan-2-yl)oxy)silane (2s)	7
Synthesis of diisopropyl(((1S,2R,5S)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)oxy)silane (2t)	8
Synthesis of ethyl (R)-2-((diisopropylsilyl)oxy)propanoate (2u)	8
Synthesis of tert-butyl 5-((diisopropylsilyl)oxy)-1H-indole-1-carboxylate (2v)	9
Synthesis of (<i>E</i>)-((3,7-dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-yl)oxy)diisopropylsilane (2w)	10
Synthesis of methyl N-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-O-(diisopropylsilyl)- <i>D</i> -serinate (2x)	10
3. Scope Studies of Ru(II)-Catalyzed Si–H Insertion on Silanes	11
3.1 General procedure E: Ru(II)-Pheox catalyzed Si–H insertion of silanes.....	11
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-(triisopropylsilyl)acetate (4a)	12
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-(triethylsilyl)acetate (4b)	12
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-(benzyl-diisopropylsilyl)acetate (4c).....	13
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(pent-4-en-1-yl)silyl)acetate (4d)	13
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-((4-chlorobutyl)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (4e).....	14
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-((3-(benzyloxy)propyl)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (4f)	14
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(vinyl)silyl)acetate (4g)	15
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(phenyl)silyl)acetate (4h)	15
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-((4-fluorophenyl)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (4i).....	16
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-(dimethyl(phenyl)silyl)acetate (4j)	16
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxisoindolin-2-yl 2-((4-chlorophenyl)dimethylsilyl)acetate (4k).....	17

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(4-((trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)phenyl)silyl)acetate (4l)	17
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(thiophen-2-yl)silyl)acetate (4m)	18
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diphenylsilyl)acetate (4n)	18
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(triphenylsilyl)acetate (4o)	19
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(phenoxy)silyl)acetate (4p)	19
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((benzyloxy)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (4q)	20
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((cyclohex-2-en-1-yloxy)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (4r)	20
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl((4-methylpentan-2-yl)oxy)silyl)acetate (4s)	21
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(((1S,2R,5S)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)oxy)silyl)acetate (4t)	21
Synthesis of ethyl (<i>R</i>)-2-(((2-((1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)oxy)-2-oxoethyl)diisopropylsilyl)oxy)propanoate (4u)	22
Synthesis of <i>tert</i> -butyl 5-(((2-((1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)oxy)-2-oxoethyl)diisopropylsilyl)oxy)-1H-indole-1-carboxylate (4v)	22
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl (<i>E</i>)-2-(((2,7-dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-yl)oxy)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (4w)	23
Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl (<i>R</i>)-3,3-diisopropyl-6-(methoxycarbonyl)-10,10-dimethyl-8-oxo-4,9-dioxo-7-aza-3-silaundecanoate (4x)	24
Synthesis of redox-active ester derived from 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (4y)	24
Synthesis of redox-active ester derived from 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (4z)	25
4. Diversification of α -Silyl Redox-Active Ester Products	26
4.1 General procedure F: One-pot methylborylation of silanes using NHPI-DA (3)	26
General procedure G: One-pot methylborylation of dimethylsilanes using a photo-induced approach	26
Synthesis of triisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1a)	28
Synthesis of triethyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1b)	28
Synthesis of benzyl diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1c)	29
Synthesis of (4-chlorobutyl)diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1e)	30
Synthesis of (3-(benzyloxy)propyl)diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1f)	30
Synthesis of diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)(vinyl)silane (1g)	31

Synthesis of diisopropyl(phenyl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1h)	32
Synthesis of (4-fluorophenyl)diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1i)	32
Synthesis of dimethyl(phenyl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1j)	33
Synthesis of (4-chlorophenyl)dimethyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1k)	34
Synthesis of ((4-(diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silyl)phenyl)ethynyl)trimethylsilane (1l).....	34
Synthesis of diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)(thiophen-2-yl)silane (1m).....	35
Synthesis of triphenyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1o)	35
Synthesis of diisopropyl(phenoxy)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1p).....	36
Synthesis of (benzyloxy)diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1q).....	36
Synthesis of diisopropyl((4-methylpentan-2-yl)oxy)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1s).....	37
Synthesis of diisopropyl(((1R,2S,5R)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)oxy)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1t).....	38
Synthesis of tert-butyl 5-((diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silyl)oxy)-1H-indole-1-carboxylate (1v)	38
Synthesis of methyl <i>N</i> -(tert-butoxycarbonyl)- <i>O</i> -((diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silyl)- <i>D</i> -serinate (1x).....	39
Synthesis of 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (1y).....	39
Synthesis of diethyl(methyl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1z) ..	40
Synthesis of 1,1,3,3-tetramethyl-1,3-bis((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)disiloxane (1aa).....	41
Synthesis of benzyldimethyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1ab) ..	41
Synthesis of (4-methylphenethyl)diphenyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1ac).....	42
Synthesis of (E)-diphenyl(styryl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1ad).....	43
5. References	44
6. NMR Spectra of Synthesized Compounds	45
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2d	45
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2d	46
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2e	47

¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2e	48
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2f	49
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2f	50
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2i	51
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2i	52
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2l	53
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2l	54
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2m	55
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2m	56
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2r	57
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2r	58
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2s	59
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2s	60
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2t	61
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2t	62
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2u	63
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2u	64
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2v'	65
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2v'	66
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2v	67
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2v	68
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2w	69
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2w	70
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2x	71
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 2x	72
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4a	73
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4a	74
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4b	75
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4b	76
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4c	77
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4c	78
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4d	79
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4d	80
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4e	81
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4e	82
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4f	83

¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4f	84
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4g	85
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4g	86
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4h	87
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4h	88
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4i	89
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4i	90
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4j	91
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4j	92
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4k	93
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4k	94
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4l	95
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4l	96
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4m	97
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4m	98
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4n	99
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4n	100
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4o	101
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4o	102
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4p	103
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4p	104
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4q	105
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4q	106
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4r	107
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4r	108
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4s	109
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4s	110
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4t	111
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4t	112
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4u	113
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4u	114
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4v	115
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4v	116
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4w	117
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4w	118
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4x	119

¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4x	120
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4y	121
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4y	122
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4z	123
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 4z	124
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1a	125
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1a	126
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1b	127
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1b	128
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1c	129
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1c	130
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1d	131
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1d	132
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1e	133
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1e	134
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1f	135
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1f	136
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1g	137
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1g	138
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1h	139
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1h	140
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1i	141
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1i	142
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1j	143
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1j	144
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1k	145
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1k	146
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1l	147
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1l	148
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1m	149
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1m	150
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1o	151
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1o	152
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1p	153
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1p	154
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1q	155

¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1q	156
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1s	157
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1s	158
HSQC-NMR (CDCl ₃) for compound 1s	159
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1t	160
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1t	161
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1v	162
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1v	163
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1x	164
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1x	165
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1y	166
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1y	167
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1z	168
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1z	169
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1aa	170
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1aa	171
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1ab	172
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1ab	173
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1ac	174
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1ac	175
HSQC-NMR (CDCl ₃) for compound 1ac	176
¹ H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1ad	177
¹³ C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl ₃) for compound 1ad	178

1. General Information

Materials: Silanes were either synthesised using the procedures described in the literature¹⁻⁸ or purchased from commercial sources, e.g.; Sigma Aldrich, Fluorochem and TCI Chemicals etc. NHPI-DA (**3**) was prepared according to the procedure developed by our group.¹⁴ Alternatively, it can be purchased from Key Organics (CAS: 816437-80-6; Product Number: SO-3001). Catalysts, [RuL₅(CH₃CN)₄]PF₆ and Fe[TPP]Cl were synthesized using the procedures described in the literature,¹⁵ Other catalysts and ligands used in this work, were purchased from aforementioned commercial sources. Dry solvents were obtained by passing them through activated alumina columns. When appropriate, degassing of anhydrous solvent was performed by bubbling argon for 30 minutes under sonication. The solvents used in column chromatography, petroleum ether, pentane, dichloromethane, methanol and ethyl acetate, were purchased from commercial suppliers in HPLC grade and used without further purification.

Chromatography: Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was carried out on 0.25 mm E. Merck silica plates (60F – 254) using UV light ($\lambda = 254$ nm) as visualizing agent and α -vanillin, phosphomolybdic acid (PMA) or KMnO₄ solution and heat as developing agents, as specified. Flash column chromatography on SiO₂ was performed using E. Merck silica oil (60 Å, particle size 0.043–0.063mm).

Characterization: NMR spectra for the characterization of compounds were recorded at room temperature on a Bruker instrument 400 MHz (¹H) and at 101 MHz (¹³C) and 376 MHz (¹⁹F), or 500 MHz (¹H) and at 126 MHz (¹³C). Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in ppm, using the residual solvent peak in CDCl₃ ($\delta_H = 7.26$ and $\delta_C = 77.16$ ppm), coupling constants (*J*) are given in hertz (Hz). Data are reported as follows: chemical shift, multiplicity (s: singlet, d: doublet, t: triplet, q: quartet, br: broad, m: multiplet), coupling constants and integration. Carbon multiplicities were assigned by DEPT and edited HSQC techniques.

High-resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were determined with a Bruker Daltonics microTOF Mass Spectrometer using an ESI ion source. 1 μ M *i*-PrOH solutions of KOH as additive was helpful for compound (**4n,aa**) were used. For compounds **2d,e,f,i,l,m,s,u,v** neither ESI-TOF, APCI-TOF ion source proved suitable to provide high-precision data; low-resolution mass spectra (LRMS) recorded on a Shimadzu GC-MS (EI) are reported instead. Melting points (m.p.) of solid samples were measured by a Melting-point apparatus (Stuart SMP 50).

Experimental details: Reactions were performed in common pyrex round bottom flasks, microwave vials 2 - 8 mL (VWR or Biotage[®]), or 5 - 20 ml flat bottom vials (Cronus, SMILabHut Ltd. or VWR[®]) crimped on top with 20 mm Sil/PTFE Septa. Reaction temperatures were maintained using Thermowatch-controlled silicone oil baths, dry ice-acetone, water-ice baths or an Immersion Cooler (Julabo-FT902) equipped with temperature controller. Slow additions were performed using Landgraf HLL LA-30 or Harvard Apparatus Pump11Elite syringe pumps.

2. Preparation of Starting Materials

The following silanes were synthesized according to the procedures reported in the literature. All the data are in accordance with the literature.¹⁻⁸

Figure 2.1: Silanes prepared according to procedure reported in the literature.

2.1 General procedure A: Preparation of Grignard-reagents

A flame-dried microwave vial was charged with Mg turnings (0.18 g, 7.5 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) and I₂ (13 mg, 0.05 mmol, 0.01 equiv.). In a separate flame-dried vial, alkyl bromide (5.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was dissolved in anhydrous THF (10.0 mL) to make a 0.5 M solution. A small portion of the alkyl bromide solution (*ca.* 2.0 mL) was added to the mixture of Mg and I₂. The vial was stirred while heated gently with a heat gun until the dark brown colour disappeared. The rest of the alkyl bromide solution (8.0 mL) was added dropwise while the vial was heated with a heat gun. After 1 h, the resulting Grignard reagent was titrated using the protocol reported by Knochel and co-workers.¹

Scheme 2.1: Freshly prepared Grignard reagents

2.2 General procedure B: Reaction of freshly prepared Grignard-reagents (using general procedure A) with diisopropylchlorosilane

To the ice-bath cooled THF solution of diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 1 equiv.), a freshly prepared (using general procedure A) or commercially available Grignard-reagent (1.1 equiv.) was added dropwise. After 3 hours of stirring the mixture was quenched with water, the aqueous layer was extracted with diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ using pentane or pentane/EtOAc as eluent to afford silanes **2c-m**.

General procedure C: Synthesis of alkoxy silanes using DMAP and triethylamine

In a 50 mL round-bottomed flask chlorodiisopropylsilane (**S1**; 1.0 equiv.) was added to a mixture of the corresponding alcohol (1.0 equiv.) and DMAP (0.1 equiv.) in tetrahydrofuran (0.3 M) at 0 °C under argon atmosphere. Triethylamine (2.0 equiv.) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was stirred for 12 h at room temperature. Upon completion, the white solid was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/ ethyl acetate = 98:2) to afford alkoxy silanes **2p-r,u-x**.

General procedure D: Synthesis of alkoxy silanes using imidazole

In a 50 mL round-bottomed flask, chlorodiisopropylsilane (**S1**; 1.0 equiv.) was added to a mixture of an alcohol (1.1 equiv.) and imidazole (1.0 equiv.) in tetrahydrofuran (0.2 M) at room temperature under argon atmosphere. The resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 14 h. Upon completion, the white solid was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/ ethyl acetate = 98:2) to afford alkoxy silanes **2s,t**.

Synthesis of diisopropyl(pent-4-en-1-yl)silane (**2d**)

General procedure B was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.9 mL, 5 mmol, 1 equiv.), pent-4-en-1-ylmagnesium bromide (**S2**; 12.5 mL, 0.44 M in THF, 3.3 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), at 0 °C to room temperature for 3 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2d** (0.46 g, 2.5 mmol, 50%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.6 (pentane/EtOAc = 98:2, stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 5.80 (ddt, *J* = 17.0, 10.2, 6.7 Hz, 1H), 5.05 – 4.93 (m, 2H), 3.44 – 3.40 (m, 1H), 2.13 – 2.05 (m, 2H), 1.53 – 1.44 (m, 2H), 1.04 – 1.01 (m, 12H), 0.62 (ddd, *J* = 11.3, 5.8, 3.2 Hz, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 138.8, 114.5, 37.6, 24.8, 19.1, 18.7, 10.6, 8.0.

GCMS traces for [C₁₁H₂₄Si] = 141 (C₈H₁₇Si), 113 (C₆H₁₃Si), 99 (C₅H₁₁Si), 85 (C₄H₉Si), 71 (C₃H₇Si).

Synthesis of (4-chlorobutyl)diisopropylsilane (**2e**)

General procedure B was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.5 mL, 3 mmol, 1 equiv.), (4-chlorobutyl)magnesium bromide (**S3**; 6.7 mL, 0.49 M in THF, 3.3 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), at 0 °C to room temperature for 3 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2e** (0.18 g, 0.87 mmol, 29%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.6 (pentane/EtOAc = 98:2, stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 3.55 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 3.46 – 3.41 (m, 1H), 1.82 (dt, *J* = 14.2, 6.8 Hz, 2H), 1.60 – 1.49 (m, 2H), 1.04 – 1.02 (m, 12H), 0.90 – 0.82 (m, 2H), 0.68 – 0.58 (m, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 44.7, 36.1, 22.6, 19.1, 18.7, 10.5, 7.6.

GCMS traces for [C₁₀H₂₃ClSi] = 163 (C₇H₁₆ClSi), 135 (C₅H₁₂ClSi), 121 (C₄H₁₀ClSi).

Synthesis of (3-(benzyloxy)propyl)diisopropylsilane (**2f**)

General procedure B was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.5 mL, 3 mmol, 1 equiv.), (3-(benzyloxy)propyl)magnesium bromide (**S4**; 10.6 mL, 0.31 M in THF, 3.3 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), at 0 °C to room temperature for 3 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2f** (0.75 g, 2.5 mmol, 84%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.6 (pentane/EtOAc = 98:2, stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.35 (d, *J* = 4.3 Hz, 4H), 7.32 – 7.26 (m, 1H), 4.52 (s, 2H), 3.46 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H), 1.72 (dt, *J* = 16.1, 6.9 Hz, 2H), 1.03 (d, *J* = 4.1 Hz, 14H), 0.71 – 0.57 (m, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 138.7, 128.3, 127.6, 127.5, 73.2, 72.8, 25.4, 19.1, 18.7, 10.6, 4.5.

GCMS traces for [C₁₆H₂₈OSi] = 264 (C₆H₂₈OSi), 91 (C₇H₇).

Synthesis of (4-fluorophenyl)diisopropylsilane (**2i**)

General procedure B was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.5 mL, 3 mmol, 1 equiv.), (4-fluorophenyl)magnesium bromide (**S5**; 4.1 mL, 0.81 M in THF, 3.3 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), at 0 °C to room temperature for 3 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2i** (0.5 g, 2.3 mmol, 79%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.4 (pentane, stains in iodine).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.52 – 7.45 (m, 2H), 7.09 – 7.02 (m, 2H), 3.94 (t, *J* = 3.1 Hz, 1H), 1.25 – 1.15 (m, 2H), 1.06 (d, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 6H), 0.98 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 6H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 165.1 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 241.9 Hz), 137.3 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 7.5 Hz), 129.5 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 4.0 Hz), 115.0 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 19.8 Hz), 18.6, 18.4, 10.7.

GCMS traces for [C₁₂H₁₉FSi] = 210 (C₁₂H₁₉FSi), 167 (C₉H₁₂FSi), 125 (C₆H₆FSi), 139 (C₇H₈FSi).

Synthesis of ((4-(diisopropylsilyl)phenyl)ethynyl)trimethylsilane (**2l**)

General procedure B was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.39 mL, 2.3 mmol, 1 equiv.), (4-((trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)phenyl)magnesium bromide (**S6**; 7.1 mL, 0.36 M in THF, 2.5 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), at 0 °C to room temperature for 3 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2l** (0.52 g, 1.8 mmol, 78%).

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.75 (pentane; UV-active and stains green in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.44 (s, 4H), 3.92 (t, *J* = 3.2 Hz, 1H), 1.22 (ddp, *J* = 10.5, 7.4, 3.2 Hz, 2H), 1.05 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 6H), 0.97 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 6H), 0.25 (s, 9H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 135.2, 135.1, 130.9, 123.7, 105.1, 94.9, 18.6, 18.4, 10.6, -0.0.

GCMS traces for [C₁₇H₂₈Si₂] = 288 (C₁₇H₂₈Si₂), 273 (C₁₆H₂₅Si₂), 245 (C₁₄H₂₁Si₂), 217 (C₁₂H₁₇Si₂).

Synthesis of diisopropyl(thiophen-2-yl)silane (**2m**)

General procedure B was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.33 mL, 2.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), thiophen-2-ylmagnesium bromide (**S7**; 5.5 mL, 0.4 M in THF, 2.2 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), at 0 °C to room temperature for 3 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane) to afford compound **2m** (0.34 g, 1.7 mmol, 87%).

Appearance: Colorless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.81 (pentane, UV-active and stains in iodine).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.64 (d, *J* = 4.6 Hz, 1H), 7.33 (d, *J* = 3.4 Hz, 1H), 7.22 (dd, *J* = 4.6, 3.4 Hz, 1H), 4.12 (t, *J* = 2.9 Hz, 1H), 1.28 – 1.17 (m, 2H), 1.06 (dd, *J* = 15.0, 7.2 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 136.6, 131.7, 131.2, 128.2, 18.7, 18.5, 11.5.

GCMS traces for [C₁₀H₁₈SSi] = 198 (C₁₀H₁₈SSi), 155 (C₇H₁₁SSi), 127 (C₅H₇SSi), 112 (C₄H₄SSi), 101 (C₅H₁₃Si).

Synthesis of (cyclohex-2-en-1-yloxy)diisopropylsilane (**2r**)

General procedure C was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.51 mL, 3.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), cyclohex-2-en-1-ol (**S8**; 0.29 mL, 3.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), DMAP (37 mg, 30 μmol, 0.1 equiv.) and triethylamine (0.83 mL, 6.0 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) in THF (0.3 M) at room temperature for 12 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2r** (0.48 g, 2.3 mmol, 75%).

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 5.78 (dtd, *J* = 6.8, 3.4, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 5.75 – 5.68 (m, 1H), 4.27 – 4.21 (m, 1H), 4.19 (t, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 2.09 – 1.98 (m, 1H), 1.98 – 1.82 (m, 2H), 1.82 – 1.73 (m, 1H), 1.67 – 1.49 (m, 2H), 1.08 – 0.94 (m, 14H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 130.4, 129.5, 68.9, 32.0, 25.0, 19.4, 17.5, 17.4, 17.4, 17.4, 12.7, 12.5.

GCMS traces for [C₁₂H₂₄OSi] = 212 (C₁₂H₂₄OSi), 169 (C₉H₁₇OSi), 89 (C₃H₉OSi), 81 (C₆H₉).

Synthesis of diisopropyl((4-methylpentan-2-yl)oxy)silane (**2s**)

General procedure D was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.85 mL, 5.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), 4-methylpentan-2-ol (**S9**; 0.70 mL, 5.5 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and imidazole (0.34 g, 5.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in THF (0.2 M) at room temperature for 14 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2s** (0.49 g, 2.2 mmol, 45%).

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.75 (pentane; stains in iodine).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 4.18 (t, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 1H), 3.95 – 3.84 (m, 1H), 1.78 – 1.65 (m, 1H), 1.45 (ddd, *J* = 13.7, 7.4, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.24 – 1.18 (m, 1H), 1.16 (d, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 3H), 1.08 – 1.00 (m, 12H), 1.00 – 0.94 (m, 2H), 0.89 (dd, *J* = 6.6, 5.4 Hz, 6H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 69.1, 49.0, 24.6, 23.6, 23.0, 22.6, 17.6, 17.5, 17.5, 17.4, 12.7, 12.6.

GCMS traces for [C₁₂H₂₈OSi] = 216 (C₁₂H₂₈OSi), 201 (C₁₁H₂₅OSi), 173 (C₉H₂₁OSi), 159 (C₈H₁₉OSi), 131 (C₆H₁₅OSi).

Synthesis of diisopropyl(((1*S*,2*R*,5*S*)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)oxy)silane (**2t**)

General procedure D was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.34 mL, 2.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (1*S*,2*R*,5*S*)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexan-1-ol (**S10**; 0.65 g, 4.2 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and imidazole (0.28 g, 4.2 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in THF (0.2 M) at room temperature for 14 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2t** (0.31 g, 1.2 mmol, 59%).

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.75 (pentane; UV-active and stains green in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 4.22 (t, J = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 3.44 (td, J = 10.3, 4.3 Hz, 1H), 2.31 – 2.20 (m, 1H), 2.01 – 1.94 (m, 1H), 1.65 – 1.56 (m, 2H), 1.42 – 1.31 (m, 1H), 1.20 – 1.12 (m, 1H), 1.06 – 1.02 (m, 12H), 1.01 – 0.92 (m, 4H), 0.90 (dd, J = 6.8, 1.6 Hz, 6H), 0.88 – 0.80 (m, 1H), 0.75 (d, J = 7.0 Hz, 3H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 74.5, 50.5, 44.9, 34.7, 31.8, 25.2, 23.0, 22.5, 21.4, 17.8, 17.8, 17.7, 17.7, 16.0, 13.1, 12.9.

HRMS (ESI-TOF) for [C₁₆H₃₄OSi+Na]⁺: 293.2271; found. 293.2273.

Synthesis of ethyl (*R*)-2-((diisopropylsilyl)oxy)propanoate (**2u**)

General procedure C was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.68 mL, 4.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), ethyl (*R*)-2-hydroxypropanoate (**S11**; 0.46 mL, 4.2 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), DMAP (49 mg, 40 μ mol, 0.1 equiv.) and triethylamine (1.1 mL, 8.0 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) in THF (0.3 M) at room temperature for 12 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2u** (0.40 g, 1.7 mmol, 43%).

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 4.34 (q, J = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 4.26 – 4.13 (m, 3H), 1.43 (d, J = 6.8 Hz, 3H), 1.28 (t, J = 7.1 Hz, 3H), 1.08 – 0.99 (m, 14H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 173.7, 70.5, 60.8, 21.0, 17.3, 17.3, 17.2 (2 CH₃Si), 14.2, 12.5, 12.4.

GCMS traces for [C₁₁H₂₄O₃Si] = 189 (C₈H₁₇O₃Si), 161 (C₆H₁₃O₃Si), 133 (C₆H₁₇OSi), 117 (C₅H₉O₃), 108 (C₇H₈O).

Synthesis of *tert*-butyl 5-((diisopropylsilyl)oxy)-1*H*-indole-1-carboxylate (2v**)**

Compound **2v'** was synthesized following the procedure reported by Huang and co-workers for a similar compound.¹⁰ A 50 mL round-bottomed flask was charged with 5-hydroxyindole (**S12**; 0.66 g, 5.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and imidazole (0.50 g, 7.5 mmol, 1.5 equiv.). The mixture was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three times). Dry DCM (0.5 M) was added followed by the dropwise addition of chlorodiisopropylsilane (**S1**; 1.0 mL, 6 mmol, 1.2 equiv.). The resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. Upon completion, the reaction mixture was then poured on water (50 mL) and extracted with DCM (3 × 50 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2v'**.

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; UV-active and stains red in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 8.00 (s, 1H), 7.24 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 1H), 7.18 – 7.14 (m, 2H), 6.85 (dd, *J* = 8.7, 2.3 Hz, 1H), 6.48 – 6.43 (m, 1H), 4.56 (d, *J* = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 1.22 – 1.07 (m, 14H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 150.3, 131.4, 128.5, 124.9, 115.4, 111.3, 109.1, 102.3, 17.4, 17.3, 12.5.

A flame-dried microwave vial was charged with 5-((diisopropylsilyl)oxy)-1*H*-indole (**2v'**; 1.2 g, 5.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), *tert*-butyl dicarbonate (1.3 g, 6.0 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) and DMAP (61 mg, 0.50 mmol, 10 mol%). The vial was evacuated and backfilled with argon (three times), followed by addition of dry acetonitrile (10 mL). The resulting mixture was heated at 80 °C overnight. Upon completion, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2v** (0.84 g, 2.5 mmol, 50%).

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; UV-active and stains red in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.97 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 7.55 (d, *J* = 3.4 Hz, 1H), 7.06 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 6.91 (dd, *J* = 8.9, 2.4 Hz, 1H), 6.46 (d, *J* = 3.7 Hz, 1H), 4.55 (t, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 1.66 (s, 9H), 1.16 – 1.03 (m, 14H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 152.2, 149.7, 131.5, 130.3, 126.5, 116.6, 115.6, 110.0, 107.0, 83.4, 28.2, 17.3, 17.2, 12.4.

HRMS (ESI-TOF) for [C₁₉H₂₉NO₃Si+Na]⁺: 370.1809; found: 370.1800.

Synthesis of (*E*)-((3,7-dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-yl)oxy)diisopropylsilane (**2w**)

General procedure C was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.51 mL, 3.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), geraniol (**S13**; 0.52 mL, 3.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), DMAP (37 mg, 30 μmol, 0.1 equiv.) and triethylamine (0.84 mL, 6.0 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) in THF (0.3 M) at room temperature for 12 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2w** (0.54 g, 2.0 mmol, 67%).

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 5.35 (dddd, *J* = 6.5, 5.2, 2.5, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 5.10 (ddt, *J* = 6.9, 5.6, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 4.26 (d, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 2H), 4.15 (t, *J* = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 2.13 – 2.07 (m, 2H), 2.06 – 1.98 (m, 2H), 1.68 (s, 3H), 1.64 (s, 3H), 1.60 (s, 3H), 1.08 – 0.96 (m, 14H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 137.8, 131.6, 124.1, 123.6, 62.5, 39.5, 26.4, 25.7, 17.7, 17.4, 17.4 (2 CH₃Si), 16.4, 12.4.

HRMS (ESI-TOF) for [C₁₆H₃₂OSi+Na]⁺: 291.2115 ; found: 291.2118.

Synthesis of methyl *N*-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)-*O*-(diisopropylsilyl)-*D*-serinate (**2x**)

General procedure C was applied using diisopropylchlorosilane (**S1**; 0.97 mL, 5.7 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), methyl (*t*-butoxycarbonyl)-*D*-serinate (**S14**; 1.2 g, 5.7 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), DMAP (70 mg, 57 μmol, 0.1 equiv.) and triethylamine (1.6 mL, 11.4 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) in THF (0.3 M) at room temperature for 12 h under argon. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 99:1 to 98:2) to afford compound **2x** (0.85 g, 2.5 mmol, 45%).

Appearance: Colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.6 (pentane/EtOAc = 95:5; stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 5.35 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 4.43 – 4.32 (m, 1H), 4.15 – 4.08 (m, 2H), 3.93 (dd, *J* = 10.1, 3.0 Hz, 1H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 1.45 (s, 9H), 1.03 – 0.97 (m, 14H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 171.1, 155.4, 79.9, 66.0, 55.6, 52.3, 28.3, 17.3, 17.2, 17.1, 17.1, 12.4, 12.2.

HRMS (ESI-TOF) for [C₁₅H₃₁NO₅Si+Na]⁺: 356.1864; found: 356.1864.

3. Scope Studies of Ru(II)-Catalyzed Si-H Insertion on Silanes

3.1 General procedure E: Ru(II)-Pheox catalyzed Si-H insertion of silanes

A flame-dried vial was charged with a stirring bar and silane (0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.). The vial was evacuated and refilled with argon (three cycles), followed by the addition of a solution of [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in dry DCM (1.0 mL). The mixture was stirred for 5 min at room temperature, followed by dropwise addition (over a period of 1 to 2 min) of a solution of *N*-hydroxyphthalimidyl diazoacetate (NHPI-DA **3**; 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in dry DCM (2.0 mL). The resulting mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. Upon completion, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (unless otherwise specified) using pentane/EtOAc to afford α-silyl NHPI esters **4a-z**.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(triisopropylsilyl)acetate (**4a**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), triisopropylsilane (**2a**; 68 μ L, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μ mol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4a** (0.10 g, 0.27 mmol, 92%).

Appearance: white solid.

TLC: R_f = 0.57 (Pentane/EtOAc = 10:1; UV-active).

m.p.: 101.2°C – 102.8°C

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.87 – 7.82 (m, 2H), 7.78 – 7.73 (m, 2H), 2.22 (s, 2H), 1.34 – 1.25 (m, 3H), 1.14 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 18H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 169.7, 162.4, 134.7, 129.2, 123.9, 18.5, 15.7, 11.4.

HRMS (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₉H₂₇NO₄Si+Na]⁺: 384.1602; found. 384.1618.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(triethylsilyl)acetate (**4b**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diethylsilane (**2b**; 53 μ L, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μ mol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4b** (73 mg, 0.23 mmol, 76%).

Appearance: white solid.

TLC: R_f = 0.43 (Pentane/EtOAc = 10:1; UV-active).

m.p.: 56.6°C – 58.5°C

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.87 – 7.85 (m, 2H), 7.77 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 2.18 (s, 2H), 1.02 (t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 9H), 0.79 (q, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 6H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 169.0, 162.4, 134.7, 129.2, 123.9, 18.6, 7.1, 3.4.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₆H₂₁NO₄Si+Na]⁺: 342.1132; found. 342.1133.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(benzylidiisopropylsilyl)acetate (**4c**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), benzyldiisopropylsilane (**2c**; 68 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[RuL5(MeCN)_4]PF_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μ mol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4c** (0.11 g, 0.28 mmol, 94%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.86 (m, 2H), 7.80 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 7.26 – 7.21 (m, 2H), 7.20 – 7.15 (m, 2H), 7.12 – 7.07 (m, 1H), 2.44 (s, 2H), 2.20 (s, 2H), 1.30 – 1.19 (m, 2H), 1.07 (dd, J = 7.4, 1.0 Hz, 12H).

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 169.2, 162.2, 138.9, 134.7, 129.0, 128.6, 128.5, 124.5, 123.9, 19.4, 17.8, 17.8, 16.4, 11.5.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[C_{23}H_{27}NO_4Si+Na]^+$: 432.1602; found. 432.1601.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(pent-4-en-1-yl)silyl)acetate (**4d**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(pent-4-en-1-yl)silane (**2d**; 61 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[RuL5(MeCN)_4]PF_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μ mol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4d** (98 mg, 0.25 mmol, 84%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 10:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.83 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 5.81 (ddt, J = 17.0, 10.2, 6.7 Hz, 1H), 5.07 – 4.93 (m, 2H), 2.19 (s, 2H), 2.11 (q, J = 7.1 Hz, 2H), 1.57 – 1.47 (m, 2H), 1.26 – 1.15 (m, 2H), 1.10 (d, J = 6.3 Hz, 12H), 0.89 – 0.82 (m, 2H).

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 169.3, 162.2, 138.5, 134.6, 129.0, 123.8, 114.8, 37.8, 23.2, 18.0, 16.6, 11.5, 9.5.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[C_{21}H_{29}NO_4Si+Na]^+$: 410.1758; found. 410: 1755.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((4-chlorobutyl)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (**4e**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (4-chlorobutyl)diisopropylsilane (**2e**; 68 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4e** (0.11 g, 0.26 mmol, 87%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.58 (Pentane/EtOAc = 8:2; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.84 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 3.57 (t, J = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 2.20 (s, 2H), 1.84 (p, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 1.63 – 1.55 (m, 2H), 1.26 – 1.14 (m, 2H), 1.10 (d, J = 6.5 Hz, 12H), 0.91 – 0.82 (m, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 169.2, 162.2, 134.6, 129.0, 123.8, 44.5, 36.2, 20.8, 18.0, 16.5, 11.6, 9.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₀H₂₈ClNO₄Si+Na]⁺: 432.1368; found: 432.1365.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((3-(benzyloxy)propyl)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (**4f**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (3-(benzyloxy)propyl)diisopropylsilane (**2f**; 87 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4f** (0.11 g, 0.23 mmol, 79%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.46 (Pentane/EtOAc = 8:2; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.88 – 7.84 (m, 2H), 7.80 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 7.36 – 7.28 (m, 4H), 7.26 – 7.21 (m, 1H), 4.51 (s, 2H), 3.48 (t, J = 6.9 Hz, 2H), 2.21 (s, 2H), 1.82 – 1.71 (m, 2H), 1.29 – 1.16 (m, 2H), 1.11 (d, J = 6.4 Hz, 12H), 0.90 – 0.83 (m, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 169.2, 162.2, 138.7, 134.6, 129.0, 128.3, 127.6, 127.4, 123.8, 73.3, 72.8, 23.9, 18.0, 16.6, 11.6, 6.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₆H₃₃NO₅Si+Na]⁺: 490.2020; found: 490.2025.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(vinyl)silyl)acetate (**4g**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(vinyl)silane (**2g**; 47 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, $3.0 \mu\text{mol}$, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4g** (95 mg, 0.27 mmol, 92%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.45 (Pentane/EtOAc = 10:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.91 – 7.85 (m, 2H), 7.81 – 7.76 (m, 2H), 6.25 – 6.08 (m, 2H), 5.88 (dd, J = 18.2, 5.7 Hz, 1H), 2.30 (s, 2H), 1.36 – 1.27 (m, 2H), 1.13 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 12H).

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 169.1, 162.3, 135.7, 134.8, 131.5, 129.5, 124.0, 17.8, 17.7, 16.4, 11.2.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_4\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 368.1289; found. 368.1295.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(phenyl)silyl)acetate (**4h**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(phenyl)silane (**2h**; 64 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, $3.0 \mu\text{mol}$, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4h** (0.11 g, 0.29 mmol, 96%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.45 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

^1H -NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.91 – 7.85 (m, 2H), 7.80 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 7.59 – 7.53 (m, 2H), 7.44 – 7.36 (m, 3H), 2.53 (s, 2H), 1.58 (hept, J = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 1.13 (dd, J = 12.5, 7.4 Hz, 12H).

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 169.1, 162.2, 134.7, 134.6, 132.3, 129.6, 129.0, 127.9, 123.9, 17.6, 17.5, 16.1, 11.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_4\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 418.1445; found. 418.1446.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((4-fluorophenyl)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (**4i**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (4-fluorophenyl)diisopropylsilane (**2i**; 69 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4i** (0.11 g, 0.27 mmol, 91%).

Appearance: white solid.

m.p.: 70.3 – 73.5 °C

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.88 – 7.84 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.76 (m, 2H), 7.59 – 7.53 (m, 2H), 7.14 – 7.07 (m, 2H), 2.50 (s, 2H), 1.55 (dt, *J* = 14.8, 7.4 Hz, 2H), 1.12 (dd, *J* = 11.2, 7.4 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.9, 165.3 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 249.2 Hz), 162.1, 136.7 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 7.6 Hz), 134.7, 129.0, 127.8 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 3.7 Hz), 123.9, 115.3 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 19.7 Hz), 17.6, 17.6, 16.3, 11.1.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₂H₂₄FNO₄Si+Na]⁺: 436.1351; found: 436.1350.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(dimethyl(phenyl)silyl)acetate (**4j**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), dimethyl(phenyl)silane (**2j**; 45 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4j** (79 mg, 0.23 mmol, 78%).

Appearance: white solid.

m.p.: 98.5 – 102.1 °C

TLC: R_f = 0.52 (Pentane/EtOAc = 8:2; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.90 – 7.86 (m, 2H), 7.80 – 7.77 (m, 2H), 7.62 – 7.60 (m, 2H), 7.42 – 7.38 (m, 3H), 2.40 (s, 2H), 0.59 (s, 6H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.3, 162.2, 135.9, 134.6, 133.6, 129.9, 129.0, 128.1, 123.9, 23.2, -3.2.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₈H₁₇NO₄Si+Na]⁺: 362.0819; found: 362.0864.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((4-chlorophenyl)dimethylsilyl)acetate (4k)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (4-chlorophenyl)dimethylsilane (**2k**; 56 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4k** (0.10 g, 0.28 mmol, 94%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.90 – 7.84 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 7.54 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.38 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 2.37 (s, 2H), 0.58 (s, 6H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.1, 162.2, 135.0, 134.7, 134.1, 129.0, 128.4, 123.9, 23.2, -3.1.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₈H₁₆ClNO₄Si+Na]⁺: 396.0429; found: 396.0439.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((diisopropyl(4-((trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)phenyl)silyl)acetate (4l)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), ((4-((diisopropylsilyl)phenyl)ethynyl)trimethylsilane (**2l**; 95 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4l** (0.13 g, 0.26 mmol, 88%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains green in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.88 – 7.84 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 7.53 – 7.46 (m, 4H), 2.50 (s, 2H), 1.60 – 1.52 (m, 2H), 1.11 (dd, *J* = 12.7, 7.4 Hz, 12H), 0.25 (s, 9H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.9, 162.1, 134.6, 134.4, 133.2, 131.2, 129.0, 124.3, 123.9, 104.9, 95.4, 17.6, 17.5, 16.0, 11.0, -0.1.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₇H₃₃NO₄Si₂+Na]⁺: 514.1845; found: 514.1840.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(thiophen-2-yl)silyl)acetate (**4m**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(thiophen-2-yl)silane (**2m**; 65 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4m** (0.12 g, 0.29 mmol, 97%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.91 – 7.83 (m, 2H), 7.80 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 7.68 (dd, *J* = 4.6, 0.8 Hz, 1H), 7.42 (dd, *J* = 3.4, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 7.26 (dd, *J* = 4.7, 3.4 Hz, 1H), 2.55 (s, 2H), 1.61 – 1.49 (m, 2H), 1.16 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 4.9 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 169.0, 162.2, 135.5, 134.6, 131.4, 129.0, 123.8, 17.7, 17.6, 16.3, 11.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₀H₂₃NO₄SSi+Na]⁺: 424.1009; found: 424.1010.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diphenylsilyl)acetate (**4n**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diphenylsilane (**2n**; 61 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by recrystallization from CHCl₃/pentane to afford compound **4n** (0.12 g, 0.26 mmol, 88%).

Appearance: white solid.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 8:2; UV-active).

m.p.: 107.3 – 110.6 °C

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.83 (m, 2H), 7.78 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 7.71 – 7.67 (m, 4H), 7.50 – 7.40 (m, 6H), 5.27 (t, *J* = 3.3 Hz, 1H), 2.76 (d, *J* = 3.4 Hz, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 167.9, 161.9, 135.3, 134.6, 130.9, 130.6, 129.0, 128.3, 123.9, 19.9.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₂H₁₇NO₄Si+Na]⁺: 410.0819; found: 410.0805.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(triphenylsilyl)acetate (**4o**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), triphenylsilane (**2o**; 86 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by filtration through Florisil (Pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4o** (0.12 g, 0.25 mmol, 85%).

Appearance: Off-white solid.

TLC: Decomposes on silica gel, not detectable.

m.p.: 210.3°C – 213.2°C

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.85 – 7.79 (m, 2H), 7.76 – 7.71 (m, 2H), 7.66 – 7.61 (m, 6H), 7.50 – 7.38 (m, 9H), 3.01 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.0, 162.0, 136.0, 134.7, 132.1, 130.5, 129.1, 128.3, 123.9, 21.1.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₈H₂₁NO₄Si+Na]⁺: 486.1132; found. 486.1130.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(phenoxy)silyl)acetate (**4p**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(phenoxy)silane (**2p**; 68 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4p** (0.10 g, 0.25 mmol, 84%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: *R_f* = 0.4 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.90 – 7.85 (m, 2H), 7.80 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 7.28 – 7.21 (m, 2H), 7.02 – 6.92 (m, 3H), 2.45 (s, 2H), 1.45 (h, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 1.18 (dd, *J* = 7.4, 3.6 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.0, 162.1, 154.6, 134.7, 129.6, 129.0, 123.9, 122.1, 120.0, 18.2, 17.0, 13.2.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₂H₂₅NO₅Si+Na]⁺: 434.1394; found: 424.1398.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((benzyloxy)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (**4q**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (benzyloxy)diisopropylsilyl acetate (**2q**; 73 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 10:1) to afford compound **4q** (0.11g, 0.26 mmol, 86%).

Appearance: colourless oil

TLC: *R_f* = 0.4 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.85 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 7.40 – 7.29 (m, 4H), 7.28 – 7.22 (m, 1H), 4.96 (s, 2H), 2.38 (s, 2H), 1.38 (h, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 1.16 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.5, 162.2, 140.6, 134.7, 129.0, 128.2, 127.1, 126.1, 123.9, 65.5, 18.2, 17.3, 17.2, 12.7.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₃H₂₇NO₅Si+Na]⁺: 448.1551; found: 448.1551.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-((cyclohex-2-en-1-yloxy)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (**4r**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (cyclohex-2-en-1-yloxy)diisopropylsilyl acetate (**2r**; 70 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4r** (0.12 g, 0.28 mmol, 93%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: *R_f* = 0.58 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.83 (m, 2H), 7.78 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 5.78 (ddt, *J* = 10.2, 3.5, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 5.74 – 5.69 (m, 1H), 4.48 – 4.45 (m, 1H), 2.34 (s, 2H), 2.07 – 1.98 (m, 1H), 1.97 – 1.83 (m, 2H), 1.81 – 1.73 (m, 1H), 1.70 – 1.62 (m, 1H), 1.60 – 1.49 (m, 1H), 1.35 – 1.22 (m, 2H), 1.13 (dd, *J* = 7.2, 2.5 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.5, 162.2, 134.6, 130.3, 129.7, 129.0, 123.8, 67.2, 32.3, 25.0, 19.3, 18.4, 17.3, 17.3, 13.1, 13.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₂H₂₉NO₅Si+Na]⁺: 438.1707; found: 438.1706.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl((4-methylpentan-2-yl)oxy)silyl)acetate (4s)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl((4-methylpentan-2-yl)oxy)silane (**2s**; 71 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4s** (0.12 g, 0.28 mmol, 94%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: *R_f* = 0.6 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.85 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 4.10 (h, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 1H), 2.33 (s, 2H), 1.67 (dh, *J* = 13.5, 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.45 (dt, *J* = 13.6, 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.31 – 1.22 (m, 3H), 1.20 (d, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 3H), 1.13 (dd, *J* = 7.1, 2.7 Hz, 12H), 0.89 (dd, *J* = 10.9, 6.6 Hz, 6H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.6, 162.2, 134.6, 129.0, 123.8, 68.1, 49.0, 24.7, 23.8, 23.1, 22.7, 18.5, 17.4, 17.3, 17.3, 17.3, 13.3, 13.2.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₂H₃₃NO₅Si+Na]⁺: 442.2020; found: 442.2025.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl 2-(diisopropyl(((1S,2R,5S)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)oxy)silyl)acetate (4t)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(((1S,2R,5S)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)oxy)silane (**2s**; 89 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4t** (0.12 g, 0.25 mmol, 86%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: $R_f = 0.6$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: $R_f = 0.7$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 4:1, UV-active).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.91 – 7.86 (m, 2H), 7.81 – 7.76 (m, 2H), 3.66 (td, $J = 10.3$, 4.3 Hz, 1H), 2.36 (s, 2H), 2.30 – 2.22 (m, 1H), 2.01 – 1.95 (m, 1H), 1.67 – 1.58 (m, 2H), 1.46 – 1.34 (m, 1H), 1.33 – 1.21 (m, 2H), 1.20 – 1.12 (m, 13H), 1.10 – 0.98 (m, 2H), 0.94 – 0.90 (m, 6H), 0.88 – 0.82 (m, 1H), 0.78 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 168.7, 162.3, 134.7, 129.2, 124.0, 73.7, 50.5, 45.5, 34.6, 31.8, 25.3, 22.8, 22.4, 21.5, 19.1, 17.6, 17.6, 17.5, 17.5, 16.0, 13.8, 13.6.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{39}\text{NO}_5\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 496.2490; found: 496.2509

Synthesis of ethyl (R)-2-(((2-((1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)oxy)-2-oxoethyl)diisopropylsilyl)oxy)propanoate (4u)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), ethyl (R)-2-(((2-((1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)oxy)-2-oxoethyl)diisopropylsilyl)oxy)propanoate (**2u**; 77 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4u** (0.10 g, 0.24 mmol, 80%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: $R_f = 0.7$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 85:15; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.84 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 4.61 (q, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.23 – 4.12 (m, 2H), 2.41 (d, $J = 12.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.32 (d, $J = 12.3$ Hz, 1H), 1.45 (d, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 3H), 1.37 – 1.23 (m, 5H), 1.12 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 12H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 173.7, 168.5, 162.1, 134.6, 129.0, 123.9, 68.8, 60.9, 21.3, 18.2, 17.2, 17.1, 17.1, 17.0, 14.2, 12.9, 12.8.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{29}\text{NO}_7\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 458.1605; found: 458.1608.

Synthesis of tert-butyl 5-(((2-((1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)oxy)-2-oxoethyl)diisopropylsilyl)oxy)-1H-indole-1-carboxylate (4v)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), *tert*-butyl 5-((diisopropylsilyl)oxy)-1*H*-indole-1-carboxylate (**2v**; 0.11 g, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4v** (0.14 g, 0.25 mmol, 83%).

Appearance: colourless oil

TLC: R_f = 0.58 (Pentane/EtOAc = 8:2; UV-active and stains red in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.99 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 7.89 – 7.84 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 7.56 (d, *J* = 3.4 Hz, 1H), 7.11 (d, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 6.94 (dd, *J* = 8.9, 2.4 Hz, 1H), 6.48 (d, *J* = 3.3 Hz, 1H), 2.47 (s, 2H), 1.66 (s, 9H), 1.48 (hept, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 1.19 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 4.2 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.1, 162.1, 150.3, 149.7, 134.6, 131.6, 130.7, 129.0, 126.7, 123.9, 117.3, 115.8, 110.9, 107.1, 83.5, 28.2, 18.2, 17.1, 13.2.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₉H₃₄N₂O₇Si+Na]⁺: 573.2027; found: 573.2029.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl (*E*)-2-(((2,7-dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-yl)oxy)diisopropylsilyl)acetate (**4w**)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (*E*)-((2,7-dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-yl)oxy)diisopropylsilane (**2w**; 89 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4w** (0.12 g, 0.26 mmol, 88%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.65 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.83 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 5.37 – 5.33 (m, 1H), 5.11 – 5.06 (m, 1H), 4.39 – 4.34 (m, 2H), 2.33 (s, 2H), 2.13 – 2.05 (m, 2H), 2.05 – 1.98 (m, 2H), 1.67 (d, *J* = 1.0 Hz, 3H), 1.63 (d, *J* = 1.0 Hz, 3H), 1.59 (d, *J* = 0.7 Hz, 3H), 1.36 – 1.23 (m, 2H), 1.13 (dd, *J* = 7.4, 2.2 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 168.6, 162.1, 137.6, 134.6, 131.6, 129.0, 124.0, 123.8, 123.7, 60.9, 39.5, 26.3, 25.7, 18.1, 17.7, 17.2, 17.2, 16.4, 12.8.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₆H₃₇NO₅Si+Na]⁺: 494.2333; found: 494.2333.

Synthesis of 1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl (R)-3,3-diisopropyl-6-(methoxycarbonyl)-10,10-dimethyl-8-oxo-4,9-dioxo-7-aza-3-silaundecanoate (4x)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), methyl *N*-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)-*O*-(diisopropylsilyl)-*D*-serinate (**2x**; 0.11 g, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4x** (0.15 g, 0.28 mmol, 95%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 7:3; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.88 – 7.83 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.74 (m, 2H), 5.57 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 4.43 – 4.37 (m, 1H), 4.25 (dd, J = 10.0, 2.9 Hz, 1H), 4.05 (dd, J = 10.0, 3.0 Hz, 1H), 3.73 (s, 3H), 2.27 (d, J = 1.0 Hz, 2H), 1.38 (s, 9H), 1.31 – 1.20 (m, 2H), 1.08 (dd, J = 7.3, 3.1 Hz, 12H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 171.0, 168.2, 162.1, 155.5, 134.7, 129.0, 123.9, 79.7, 64.6, 55.5, 52.3, 28.3, 17.8, 17.0, 17.0, 17.0, 12.6, 12.5.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₅H₃₆N₂O₉Si+Na]⁺: 559.2080; found: 559.2083.

Synthesis of redox-active ester derived from 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (4y)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (**2y**; 82 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4y** (0.12 g, 0.28 mmol, 88%).

Appearance: white solid.

m.p.: 110.8 – 113.5 °C

TLC: R_f = 0.45 (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.89 – 7.84 (m, 2H), 7.78 – 7.75 (m, 2H), 2.25 (s, 2H), 0.26 (s, 27H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 170.7, 162.0, 134.6, 129.0, 123.8, 12.2, 0.6.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₉H₃₃NO₄Si₄+Na]⁺: 474.1379; found: 474.1376.

Synthesis of redox-active ester derived from 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (4z)

General procedure E was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (**2y**; 82 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 0.5 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane/EtOAc = 9:1) to afford compound **4z** (0.14 g, 0.28 mmol, 95%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.4 (Pentane/EtOAc = 8:2; UV-active and stains in permanganate).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.91 – 7.85 (m, 4H), 7.81 – 7.76 (m, 4H), 2.52 (s, 4H), 1.16 – 1.11 (m, 6H), 1.09 – 1.01 (m, 4H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 168.0, 162.1, 134.7, 129.0, 123.9, 18.6, 6.7, 3.6.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 517.1038; found: 517.1048.

4. Diversification of α -Silyl Redox-Active Ester Products

4.1 General procedure F: One-pot methylborylation of silanes using NHPI-DA (3)

The procedure has been adapted from the one reported by Baran and co-workers.¹¹

A flame-dried vial was charged with a stirring bar and silane (2a-z; 1.1 equiv.). The vial was evacuated and refilled with argon (three cycles), followed by the addition of a solution of $[RuL5(MeCN)_4]PF_6$ (0.01 equiv.) in dry DCM. The mixture was stirred for 5 min at room temperature, followed by dropwise addition (over a period of 1 to 2 min) of a solution of *N*-hydroxyphthalimidoyl diazoacetate (3; NHPI-DA; 0.2-0.3 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in dry DCM. The resulting mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. Upon completion, DCM was evaporated under reduced pressure and remaining solvent was dried using high vacuum and the crude was used for the next step without further purification.

To the vial containing the crude redox-active ester of silane (1.0 equiv.) were added B_2pin_2 (3.0 equiv.), $Cu(acac)_2$ (30 mol%), $LiOH \cdot H_2O$ (15 equiv.) and $MgCl_2$ (1.5 equiv.). The vial was evacuated and backfilled with argon (3 times), followed by addition of degassed dioxane/DMF (4:1, 0.14 M). The resulting mixture was stirred vigorously at room temperature for 10 min until a dark brown color was observed. Upon completion, the reaction mixture was diluted with Et_2O (10 mL) and transferred to a 20 mL vial containing saturated aqueous NH_4Cl solution (5 mL), and the resulting mixture was shaken vigorously until a clear biphasic solution was observed. The organic phase was collected and the aqueous phase was extracted with Et_2O (2 x 10 mL). The combined organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/ $EtOAc$ = 98:2) to afford the (borylmethyl)silanes 1a-aa.

General procedure G: One-pot methylborylation of dimethylsilanes using a photo-induced approach

The procedure has been adapted from the one reported by Aggarwal and co-workers.¹²

A flame-dried vial was charged with a stirring bar and silanes (2d,k,l,z; 1.1 equiv.). The vial was evacuated and refilled with argon (three cycles), followed by the addition of a solution of $[RuL5(MeCN)_4]PF_6$ (0.01 equiv.) in dry DCM. The mixture was stirred for 5 min at room

temperature, followed by dropwise addition (over a period of 1 to 2 min) of a solution of *N*-hydroxyphthalimidyl diazoacetate (**3**; NHPI-DA; 0.2-0.3 mmol; 1.0 equiv.) in dry DCM. The resulting mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. Upon completion, DCM was evaporated under reduced pressure and remaining solvent was dried using high vacuum and the crude was used for the next step without further purification.

To the vial containing the crude redox-active ester of silane (1 equiv.) was added B₂cat₂ (1.25 equiv.), followed by addition of anhydrous DMAc (0.1 M). Next, the headspace of the vial was purged with argon for 15-20 sec. Then the vial was closed with a cap fitted with a rubber septum. The resulting mixture was irradiated with blue light for 14 h. Upon completion, pinacol (4.0 equiv.) dissolved in triethylamine (30.0 equiv.) was added and the resulting mixture was stirred for 1 h. The reaction mixture was transferred to a 20 mL vial and diluted with diethyl ether (10 mL), followed addition of saturated NH₄Cl (5 mL) and water (5 mL). The resulting mixture was stirred vigorously until a clear biphasic solution was obtained. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with diethylether (2 x 10 mL). The combined organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford the (borylmethyl)silanes **1d,k,l,z**.

Synthesis of triisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1a**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), triisopropylsilane (**2a**; 52 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1a** (51 mg, 0.17 mmol, 57%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.75 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 1.22 (s, 12H), 1.06 – 0.98 (m, 21H), 0.00 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 82.6, 25.0, 18.7, 12.1.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₆H₃₅BO₂Si+Na]⁺: 321.2395; found: 321.2397.

Synthesis of triethyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1b**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 46 mg, 0.20 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), triethylsilane (**2b**; 26 mg, 0.22 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.2 mg, 2.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.15 g, 0.60 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (16 mg, 60 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.13 g, 3.0 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (29 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 1.4 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1b** (31 mg, 0.12 mmol, 60%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.6 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 1.23 (s, 12H), 0.94 (t, J = 7.9 Hz, 9H), 0.54 (q, J = 7.9 Hz, 6H), 0.04 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 82.6, 24.9, 7.4, 5.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[C_{13}H_{29}BO_2Si+Na]^+$: 279.1925; found: 279.1958.

Synthesis of benzyldiisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1c)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), benzyldiisopropylsilane (**2c**; 68 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[RuL5(MeCN)_4]PF_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μ mol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $Cu(acac)_2$ (24 mg, 90 μ mol, 30 mol%), $LiOH \cdot H_2O$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and $MgCl_2$ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1c** (69 mg, 0.20 mmol, 66%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.6 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 7.21 – 7.15 (m, 2H), 7.15 – 7.11 (m, 2H), 7.07 – 7.01 (m, 1H), 2.20 (s, 2H), 1.24 (s, 12H), 0.97 (s, 14H), 0.03 (s, 2H).

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 140.8, 128.6, 128.1, 123.8, 82.7, 25.0, 21.4, 18.1, 18.1, 12.3.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[C_{20}H_{35}BO_2Si+Na]^+$: 369.2396; found: 369.2391.

Synthesis of diisopropyl(pent-4-en-1-yl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1d)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(pent-4-en-1-yl)silane (**2d**; 61 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[RuL5(MeCN)_4]PF_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μ mol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $Cu(acac)_2$ (24 mg, 90 μ mol, 30 mol%), $LiOH \cdot H_2O$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and $MgCl_2$ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1d** (33 mg, 0.10 mmol, 34%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: $R_f = 0.55$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 5.80 (ddt, $J = 17.0, 10.2, 6.7$ Hz, 1H), 5.07 – 4.87 (m, 2H), 2.09 – 2.04 (m, 2H), 1.51 – 1.40 (m, 2H), 1.22 (s, 12H), 1.07 – 0.96 (m, 14H), 0.64 – 0.54 (m, 2H), 0.00 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 139.1, 114.4, 82.6, 38.2, 25.0, 23.6, 18.3, 18.3, 12.4, 11.2.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{37}\text{BO}_2\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 347.2552; found: 347.2558.

Synthesis of (4-chlorobutyl)diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1e)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (4-chlorobutyl)diisopropylsilane (**2e**; 68 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1e** (64 mg, 0.18 mmol, 61%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: $R_f = 0.5$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 3.55 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 1.79 (p, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 2H), 1.51 (dtd, $J = 11.6, 8.5, 6.3$ Hz, 2H), 1.22 (s, 12H), 1.03 – 0.88 (m, 14H), 0.62 – 0.54 (m, 2H), 0.01 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 82.6, 44.7, 36.7, 25.0, 21.4, 18.3, 12.4, 10.8.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{36}\text{BClO}_2\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 369.2162; found: 369.2167.

Synthesis of (3-(benzyloxy)propyl)diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1f)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (3-(benzyloxy)propyl)diisopropylsilane (**2f**; 98 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$

(1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1f** (49 mg, 0.12 mmol, 40%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.4 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.35 – 7.26 (m, 5H), 4.51 (s, 2H), 3.43 (t, J = 7.0 Hz, 2H), 1.68 (dt, J = 14.3, 7.2 Hz, 2H), 1.21 (s, 12H), 1.07 – 0.90 (m, 14H), 0.64 – 0.54 (m, 2H), 0.01 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 138.8, 128.3, 127.6, 127.4, 82.6, 73.8, 72.7, 25.0, 24.3, 18.3, 12.4, 7.4.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{41}\text{BO}_3\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 427.2815; found: 427.2816.

*Synthesis of diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)(vinyl)silane (**1g**)*

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(vinyl)silane (**2g**; 47 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1g** (35 mg, 0.12 mmol, 41%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.45 (Pentane/EtOAc = 99:1; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 6.15 – 5.99 (m, 2H), 5.76 (dd, J = 18.7, 5.7 Hz, 1H), 1.22 (s, 12H), 1.09 – 0.92 (m, 14H), 0.09 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 135.5, 133.1, 82.7, 24.9, 18.0, 17.8, 11.9.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}\text{BO}_2\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 305.2082; found: 305.2088.

Synthesis of diisopropyl(phenyl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1h**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(phenyl)silane (**2h**; 63 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1h** (63 mg, 0.19 mmol, 63%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.60 – 7.53 (m, 2H), 7.35 – 7.29 (m, 3H), 1.29 – 1.19 (m, 2H), 1.19 (s, 12H), 1.04 (d, J = 7.3 Hz, 6H), 0.98 (d, J = 7.4 Hz, 6H), 0.33 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 136.2, 134.9, 128.5, 127.3, 82.8, 24.9, 18.0, 17.8, 12.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₉H₃₃BO₂Si+Na]⁺: 355.2239; found: 355.2236.

Synthesis of (4-fluorophenyl)diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1i**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (4-fluorophenyl)diisopropylsilane (**2i**; 69 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1i** (56 mg, 0.16 mmol, 53%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.53 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.56 – 7.51 (m, 2H), 7.05 – 7.00 (m, 2H), 1.25 – 1.15 (m, 14H), 1.02 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 6H), 0.96 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 6H), 0.31 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 164.8 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 247.8 Hz), 136.8 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 7.4 Hz), 131.7 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 3.9 Hz), 114.3 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 19.2 Hz), 82.8, 24.9, 17.9, 17.7, 12.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₉H₃₂BFO₂Si+Na]⁺: 373.2145; found: 373.2143.

Synthesis of dimethyl(phenyl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1j)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), dimethyl(phenyl)silane (**2j**; 45 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1j** (17 mg, 60 μmol, 20%).

General procedure G was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), dimethyl(phenyl)silane (**2j**; 45 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂cat₂ (89 mg, 0.37 mmol, 1.25 equiv.), pinacol (0.14 g, 1.2 mmol, 4.0 equiv.) and Et₃N (1.3 mL, 9.0 mmol, 30 equiv.) were added and stirred in DMAc (0.1 M) under blue light irradiation for 14 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1j** (52 mg, 0.19 mmol, 63%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.65 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.58 – 7.52 (m, 2H), 7.37 – 7.31 (m, 3H), 1.18 (s, 12H), 0.36 (s, 2H), 0.33 (s, 6H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 140.2, 133.4, 128.8, 127.6, 82.8, 24.9, -0.9.

All the data are in accordance with the literature.¹³

Synthesis of (4-chlorophenyl)dimethyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1k**)

General procedure G was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (4-chlorophenyl)dimethylsilane (**2k**; 56 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2cat_2 (89 mg, 0.37 mmol, 1.25 equiv.), pinacol (0.14 g, 1.2 mmol, 4.0 equiv.) and Et_3N (1.3 mL, 9.0 mmol, 30 equiv.) were added and stirred in DMAc (0.1 M) under blue light irradiation for 14 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1k** (56 mg, 0.18 mmol, 60%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.47 (d, J = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 7.31 (d, J = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 1.18 (s, 12H), 0.34 (s, 2H), 0.31 (s, 6H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 138.5, 135.1, 134.9, 127.8, 82.9, 24.9, -0.9.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{BClO}_2\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 333.1222; found: 333.1222.

Synthesis of ((4-(diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silyl)phenyl)ethynyl)trimethylsilane (**1l**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), ((4-(diisopropylsilyl)phenyl)ethynyl)trimethylsilane (**2l**; 95 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1l** (67 mg, 0.16 mmol, 52%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (Pentane/EtOAc = 99:1; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.50 (d, J = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 7.41 (d, J = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 1.26 – 1.18 (s, 14H), 1.01 (d, J = 7.3 Hz, 6H), 0.94 (d, J = 7.4 Hz, 6H), 0.31 (s, 2H), 0.24 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 137.4, 134.7, 130.6, 123.0, 105.4, 94.4, 82.8, 24.9, 17.9, 17.7, 12.0, 0.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₄H₄₁BO₂Si₂+Na]⁺: 451.2634; found: 451.2635.

Synthesis of diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)(thiophen-2-yl)silane (**1m**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(thiophen-2-yl)silane (**2m**; 66 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1m** (55 mg, 0.16 mmol, 54%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.59 (d, *J* = 4.6 Hz, 1H), 7.36 (d, *J* = 3.2 Hz, 1H), 7.19 (t, *J* = 3.9 Hz, 1H), 1.21 (s, 14H), 1.04 (dd, *J* = 13.2, 7.3 Hz, 12H), 0.38 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 135.7, 135.3, 130.3, 127.7, 82.9, 24.9, 17.9, 17.7, 12.9.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₇H₃₁BO₂SSi+Na]⁺: 361.1803; found: 361.1804.

Synthesis of triphenyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1o**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), triphenylsilane (**2o**; 86 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (3 mL, 0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1o** (44 mg, 0.11 mmol, 36%).

Appearance: white solid.

TLC: $R_f = 0.65$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

m.p.: 94-5 – 98.3 °C

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.58 – 7.56 (m, 6H), 7.40 – 7.32 (m, 9H), 1.01 (s, 12H), 0.95 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 136.2, 135.7, 129.2, 127.6, 83.0, 24.7.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₅H₂₉BO₂Si+Na]⁺: 423.1927; found: 423.1923.

Synthesis of diisopropyl(phenoxy)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1p)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(phenoxy)silane (**2p**; 69 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μ mol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μ mol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1p** (38 mg, 0.11 mmol, 38%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: $R_f = 0.5$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.20 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 6.93 – 6.89 (m, 3H), 1.20 (s, 12H), 1.17 – 1.04 (m, 14H), 0.30 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 155.7, 129.2, 121.1, 120.3, 82.9, 24.9, 17.4, 14.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₁₉H₃₃BO₃Si+Na]⁺: 371.2188; found: 371.2186.

Synthesis of (benzyloxy)diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (1q)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (benzyloxy)diisopropylsilane (**2q**; 73 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆

(1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1q** (55 mg, 0.15 mmol, 51%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.39 – 7.34 (m, 2H), 7.34 – 7.29 (m, 2H), 7.25 – 7.20 (m, 1H), 4.83 (s, 2H), 1.21 (s, 12H), 1.09 – 1.03 (m, 14H), 0.25 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 141.6, 128.0, 126.6, 126.0, 82.8, 64.9, 24.9, 17.6, 17.6, 13.7.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{35}\text{BO}_3\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 385.2345; found: 385.2340.

*Synthesis of diisopropyl((4-methylpentan-2-yl)oxy)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1s**)*

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl((4-methylpentan-2-yl)oxy)silane (**2s**; 71 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1s** (25 mg, 70 μmol , 32%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 3.95 (h, J = 6.2 Hz, 1H), 1.66 (dp, J = 13.4, 6.7 Hz, 1H), 1.41 (dt, J = 13.6, 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.22 – 1.18 (m, 13H), 1.13 (d, J = 6.0 Hz, 3H), 1.05 – 1.00 (m, 12H), 0.98 – 0.91 (m, 2H), 0.90 – 0.85 (m, 6H), 0.17 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 82.7, 66.9, 49.3, 24.9, 24.9, 24.7, 23.9, 23.2, 22.8, 17.6, 17.6, 17.6, 14.2, 14.0.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{41}\text{BO}_3\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 376.2814; found: 376.2840.

Synthesis of diisopropyl(((1*R*,2*S*,5*R*)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)oxy)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1t**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diisopropyl(((1*R*,2*S*,5*R*)-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl)oxy)silane (**2t**; 89 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1t** (35 mg, 0.09 mmol, 28%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.6 (Pentane/EtOAc = 96:4; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 3.51 (td, *J* = 10.3, 4.3 Hz, 1H), 2.29 (pd, *J* = 7.0, 2.5 Hz, 1H), 1.98 – 1.90 (m, 1H), 1.65 – 1.54 (m, 2H), 1.39 – 1.29 (m, 1H), 1.22 (s, 12H), 1.16 – 1.08 (m, 1H), 1.06 – 0.98 (m, 13H), 0.99 – 0.92 (m, 3H), 0.90 – 0.87 (m, 6H), 0.81 (dd, *J* = 12.1, 3.1 Hz, 1H), 0.73 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 3H), 0.18 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 82.7, 72.4, 50.5, 45.6, 34.6, 31.7, 25.0, 24.9, 24.8, 22.7, 22.4, 21.5, 17.8, 17.8, 17.8, 17.7, 15.9, 14.8, 14.3.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₃H₄₇BO₃Si+Na]⁺: 433.3285; found: 433.3284.

Synthesis of *tert*-butyl 5-((diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silyl)oxy)-1*H*-indole-1-carboxylate (**1v**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), *tert*-butyl 5-((diisopropylsilyl)oxy)-1*H*-indole-1-carboxylate (**2v**; 80 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1v** (33 mg, 70 μmol, 32%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: $R_f = 0.45$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.93 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.53 (d, $J = 4.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.07 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.91 (dd, $J = 8.9, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.44 (d, $J = 3.6$ Hz, 1H), 1.65 (s, 9H), 1.20 (s, 12H), 1.18 – 1.11 (m, 2H), 1.08 (t, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 12H), 0.32 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 151.5, 149.8, 131.4, 130.2, 126.3, 117.8, 115.4, 111.1, 107.1, 83.3, 82.9, 28.2, 24.9, 17.5, 17.4, 13.9.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{42}\text{BNO}_5\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 510.2822; found: 510.2820.

Synthesis of methyl N-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-O-(diisopropyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silyl)-D-serinate (1x)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), methyl *N*-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)-*O*-(diisopropylsilyl)-*D*-serinate (**2x**; 0.11 g, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1x** (59 mg, 0.12 mmol, 41%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: $R_f = 0.5$ (Pentane/EtOAc = 9:1; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 5.64 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.36 (dt, $J = 8.8, 3.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.13 (dd, $J = 9.9, 3.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.92 (d, $J = 3.1$ Hz, 1H), 3.72 (s, 3H), 1.45 (s, 9H), 1.26 (s, 2H), 1.24 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 12H), 1.01 – 0.96 (m, 12H), 0.13 (d, $J = 5.3$ Hz, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 171.4, 155.7, 83.5, 83.0, 79.7, 63.9, 55.7, 52.1, 28.4, 25.0, 24.9, 24.8, 17.4, 17.4, 17.3, 13.5, 13.3.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{44}\text{BNO}_7\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 496.2877; found: 496.2874.

Synthesis of 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (1y)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexamethyl-2-(trimethylsilyl)trisilane (**2y**; 42 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1y** (51 mg, 0.13 mmol, 44%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.45 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 1.23 (s, 12H), 0.16 (s, 27H), 0.04 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 82.7, 25.2, 0.7.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{41}\text{BO}_2\text{Si}_4+\text{Na}]^+$: 411.2173; found: 411.2170.

*Synthesis of diethyl(methyl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1z**)*

General procedure G was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 0.14 g, 0.60 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), diethylsilane (**2z**; 26 mg, 0.30 mmol, 0.50 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (3.6 mg, 6.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2cat_2 (0.18 g, 0.75 mmol, 1.25 equiv.), pinacol (0.28 g, 2.4 mmol, 4.0 equiv.) and Et_3N (3.0 mL, 18 mmol, 30 equiv.) were added and stirred in DMAc (0.1 M) under blue light irradiation for 14 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1z** (17 mg, 70 μmol , 23%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 1.23 (s, 12H), 0.93 (t, J = 7.9 Hz, 6H), 0.52 (q, J = 7.8 Hz, 4H), 0.06 (s, 2H), 0.00 (s, 3H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 82.6, 24.9, 7.3, 6.8, -4.3.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{27}\text{BO}_2\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 265.1768; found: 265.1763.

Synthesis of 1,1,3,3-tetramethyl-1,3-bis((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)disiloxane (**1aa**)

General procedure G was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 0.93 g, 0.40 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), 1,1,3,3-tetramethyldisiloxane (**2aa**; 27 mg, 0.20 mmol, 0.50 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (2.3 mg, 4.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2cat_2 (0.12 g, 0.50 mmol, 1.25 equiv.), pinacol (0.19 g, 1.6 mmol, 4.0 equiv.) and Et_3N (1.7 mL, 12 mmol, 30 equiv.) were added and stirred in DMAc (0.1 M) under blue light irradiation for 14 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1aa** (26 mg, 63 μmol , 16%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.55 (Pentane/EtOAc = 19:1; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 1.22 (s, 24H), 0.21 (s, 4H), 0.12 (s, 12H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 82.7, 24.9, 2.2.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{40}\text{B}_2\text{O}_5\text{Si}_2+\text{Na}]^+$: 437.2500; found: 437.2502.

Synthesis of benzyldimethyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1ab**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), benzyldimethylsilane (**2ab**; 50 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1ab** (20 mg, 70 μmol , 23%).

General procedure G was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), benzyldimethylsilane (**2ab**; 50 mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2cat_2 (89 mg, 0.37 mmol, 1.25 equiv.), pinacol (0.14 g, 1.2 mmol, 4.0 equiv.) and Et_3N (1.3 mL, 9.0 mmol, 30 equiv.) were added and stirred in DMAc (0.1 M) under blue light irradiation for 14 h at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1ab** (57 mg, 0.20 mmol, 65%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.75 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.20 (t, J = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 7.06 (d, J = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 7.02 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 2.12 (s, 2H), 1.24 (s, 12H), 0.09 (s, 2H), 0.02 (s, 6H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 140.2, 128.2, 128.1, 123.9, 82.8, 27.3, 25.0, -1.8.

All the data are in accordance with the literature.¹³

*Synthesis of (4-methylphenethyl)diphenyl((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1ac**)*

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (4-methylphenethyl)diphenylsilane (**2ac**; 0.10 g, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $[\text{RuL5}(\text{MeCN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol , 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B_2pin_2 (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ (24 mg, 90 μmol , 30 mol%), $\text{LiOH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO_2 (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1ac** (39 mg, 0.10 mmol, 29%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 7.61 – 7.55 (m, 4H), 7.40 – 7.31 (m, 6H), 7.13 – 7.04 (m, 4H), 2.73 – 2.65 (m, 2H), 2.31 (s, 3H), 1.53 – 1.45 (m, 2H), 1.09 (s, 12H), 0.71 (s, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 142.3, 136.8, 134.8, 134.8, 129.1, 128.9, 127.7, 82.9, 29.3, 24.8, 21.0, 16.9.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for $[\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{35}\text{BO}_2\text{Si}+\text{Na}]^+$: 465.2397; found: 465.2399.

Synthesis of (*E*)-diphenyl(styryl)((4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)methyl)silane (**1ad**)

General procedure F was applied using NHPI-DA (**3**; 69 mg, 0.30 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), (*E*)-diphenyl(styryl)silane (**2ad**; 94 Mg, 0.33 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and [RuL5(MeCN)₄]PF₆ (1.8 mg, 3.0 μmol, 0.01 equiv.) in DCM (0.1 M) for 30 min at room temperature to obtain the crude redox-active ester. Then, B₂pin₂ (0.23 g, 0.90 mmol, 3.0 equiv.), Cu(acac)₂ (24 mg, 90 μmol, 30 mol%), LiOH·H₂O (0.19 g, 4.5 mmol, 15 equiv.) and MgCl₂ (43 mg, 0.45 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were added and stirred in dioxane/DMF (4:1, 2.1 mL, 0.14 M) for 10 min at room temperature. The crude was purified by flash chromatography on SiO₂ (pentane to pentane/EtOAc = 98:2) to afford compound **1ad** (31 mg, 70 μmol, 24%).

Appearance: colourless oil.

TLC: R_f = 0.5 (Pentane/EtOAc = 98:2; stains blue in vanillin).

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.64 – 7.60 (m, 4H), 7.48 – 7.44 (m, 2H), 7.41 – 7.30 (m, 8H), 7.28 – 7.24 (m, 1H), 7.00 (d, *J* = 19.1 Hz, 1H), 6.81 (d, *J* = 19.1 Hz, 1H), 1.08 (s, 12H), 0.81 (s, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 147.4, 138.2, 136.3, 135.3, 129.2, 128.5, 128.2, 127.7, 126.7, 125.1, 83.0, 24.8.

HRMS: (ESI-TOF) calc. for [C₂₇H₃₁BO₂Si+H]⁺: 427.2084; found: 427.2082.

5. References

1. Krasovskiy, A.; Knochel, P. *Synthesis* **2006**, *5*, 0890-0891.
2. Moriguchi, T.; Moki, D.; Sekiguchi, T.; Kato, T.; Shinozuka, K. *Chem. Lett.* **2015**, *44*, 44-46.
3. Omann, L.; Pudasaini, B.; Irran, E.; Klare, H. F. T.; Baik, M. H.; Oestreich, M. *Chem. Sci.*, **2018**, *9*, 5600-5607.
4. Dutta, U.; Maiti, S.; Pimparkar, S.; Maiti, S.; Gahan, L. R.; Krenske, E. H.; Lupton, D. W.; Maiti, D. *Chem. Sci.* **2019**, *10*, 7426-7432.
5. Kan, S. B. J.; Lewis, R. D.; Chenand, K.; Arnold, F. H. *Science* **2016**, *354*, 1048-1051.
6. Lee, S.; Lee, H.; Tan, K. L. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 18778-18781.
7. Zhao, W. T.; Lu, Z. Q.; Zheng, H.; Xue, X. S.; Zhao, D. *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, 7997-8005.
8. Wang, C.; Teo, W. J.; Ge, S. *ACS Catal.* **2017**, *7*, 855-863.
9. Wu, C.; Teo, W. J.; Ge, S. *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, 5896-5900.
10. Huang, Z.; Kwon, O.; Huang, H.; Fadli, A.; Marat, X.; Moreau, M.; Lumb, J. P. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 11963-11967.
11. Wang, J.; Shang, M.; Lundberg, H.; Feu, K. S.; Hecker, S. J.; Qin, T.; Blackmond, D. G.; Baran, P. S. *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, 9537-9542.
12. Fawcett, A.; Pradeilles, J.; Wang, Y.; Mutsuga, T.; Myers, E. L.; Aggarwal, V. K. *Science* **2017**, *357*, 283-286.
13. Shu, C.; Noble, A.; Aggarwal, V. K. *Nature* **2020**, *586*, 714-719.
14. Montesinos-Magraner, M.; Costantini, M.; Ramírez-Contreras, R.; Muratore, M. E.; Johansson, M. J.; Mendoza, A. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58* (18), 5930-5935.
15. (a) Chanthamath, S.; Thongjareun, S.; Shibatomi, K.; Iwasa, S. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2012**, *53*, 4862-4865. (b) Sun, Z.-C.; She, Y.-B.; Zhou, Y.; Song, X.-F.; Li, K. *Molecules* **2011**, *16*, 2960-2970.

6. NMR Spectra of Synthesized Compounds

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2d**

SI-45

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2d**

SI-46

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2e**

SI-47

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2e**

- 44.66
- 36.09
- ~ 22.55
- ~ 19.06
- ~ 18.71
- 10.51
- 7.61

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2f**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2f**

SI-50

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2i**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2i**

SI-52

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2I**

SI-53

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2I**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2m**

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2m**

SI-56

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2r**

SI-57

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2r**

SI-58

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2s**

SI-59

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2s**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2t**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2t**

SI-62

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2u**

SI-63

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2u**

SI-64

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2v'**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2v'**

SI-66

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2v**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2v**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2w**

SI-69

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2w**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **2x**

SI-71

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **2x**

SI-72

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4a**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4a**

SI-74

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4b**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4b**

SI-76

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4c**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4c**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4d**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4d**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4e**

SI-81

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4e**

SI-82

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4f**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4f**

SI-84

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4g**

SI-85

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4g**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4h**

SI-87

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4h**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4i**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4i**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4j**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4j**

SI-92

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4k**

SI-93

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4k**

SI-94

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4I**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4I**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4m**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4m**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4n**

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4n**

SI-100

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4o**

7.83
7.82
7.82
7.81
7.80
7.80
7.75
7.75
7.74
7.73
7.73
7.72
7.71
7.65
7.65
7.64
7.64
7.63
7.63
7.50
7.50
7.49
7.49
7.48
7.47
7.46
7.46
7.45
7.44
7.44
7.43
7.42
7.41
7.41
7.40

SI-101

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4o**

SI-102

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4p**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4p**

SI-104

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4q**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4q**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4r**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4r**

SI-108

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4s**

SI-109

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4s**

SI-110

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4t**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4t**

SI-112

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4u**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4u**

SI-114

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4v**

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4v**

SI-116

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4w**

SI-117

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **4w**

SI-118

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound 4x

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4x**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4y**

SI-121

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4y**

SI-122

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4z**

SI-123

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **4z**

SI-124

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1a**

SI-125

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1a**

SI-126

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1b**

SI-127

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1b**

SI-128

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1c**

SI-129

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1c**

SI-130

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1d**

SI-131

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1d**

SI-132

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1e**

SI-133

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1e**

SI-134

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1f**

SI-135

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1f**

SI-136

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1g**

SI-137

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1g**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1h**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1h**

SI-140

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1i**

SI-141

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1i**

SI-142

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1j**

SI-143

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1j**

SI-144

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1k**

SI-145

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1k**

SI-146

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1I**

SI-147

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **11**

SI-148

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1m**

SI-149

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1m**

SI-150

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1o**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1o**

SI-152

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1p**

SI-153

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1p**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1q**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1q**

SI-156

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1s**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1s**

SI-158

HSQC-NMR (CDCl₃) for compound **1s**

SI-159

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1t**

SI-160

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1t**

SI-161

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1v**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1v**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1x**

SI-164

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1x**

SI-165

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1y**

SI-166

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1y**

SI-167

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1z**

SI-168

¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1z**

SI-169

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1aa**

SI-170

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1aa**

SI-171

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1ab**

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1ab**

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1ac**

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1ac**

SI-175

HSQC-NMR ($CDCl_3$) for compound **1ac**

SI-176

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **1ad**

SI-177

^{13}C -NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) for compound **1ad**

